

ABOUT THE MEANING OF THE GARDEN OF EDEN AND PARADISE: WHAT DOES EACH OF THEM REPRESENT?

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the complex and dissonant theme of the meaning of the Garden of Eden and Paradise, in an attempt to understand what each of them represents in the semantic universe. In the passages of the Bible described in the book of Genesis, the references are always in relation to a garden and even this expression needs to be properly analyzed, because Eden was a very large region that, on the eastern side, presented an exuberant natural beauty with springs that formed four historic rivers and endowed with very valuable minerals. Therefore, the measure of comparison between the southern and northern regions of Eden was taken as a peaceful object of comparison and it was possible to arrive at the idea that it was a paradisiacal condition, given the geological, geographical position and climatological conditions. It was after the speeches of Jesus of Nazareth in relation to children that the priests of the Middle Ages created the false idea that childhood represents the most sublime spiritual purity and, based on the work of Rousseau, in the 17th century, this ended up being consolidating through common sense, becoming a dogma until Sigmund, in the 20th century, casts aside the entire ideology of affective purity of children and the metaphorical comparison of the Garden of Eden and childhood as being representations of paradise begin to be peaceful objects of questioning.

Keywords: Garden of Eden; Childhood; Metaphors; Allegories.

INTRODUCTION

The Garden of Eden is an allegory and cannot be understood as being more than that, when taken from a hermeneutic interpretation of the biblical text, narrated by Moses, the Hebrew prophet. The perfection with which it is portrayed enchants due to its description of beauty and, at the same time, because it contains two elements that determine human biological development: gonadotrophic maturity, which results in the desire for union with others, and cognitive development, which culminates in knowledge and the constant need for it, fueled through doubt.

In the same condition of development of poetic thought, the aforementioned paradise can be interpreted as a metaphor, in which every human being is trapped, conditioning the species and two other metaphorical figures were placed in this world, highlighting the serpent that, for ages very remote mythological, represents fertility, in which several cultures highlighted their goddesses- *mater* under this symbolism and, the tree that produces the fruit of knowledge, this being none other than, if not, curiosity.

The first concern that the reader should have, when proposing to read an epic text, is to seek to understand, in depth, the sociological characteristics that determine the thinking of the people about whom the treatise refers. Stories and legends and how they symbolically represent life, existence and events, all of this leads to a pertinent approach to what can be understood about the literary productions that permeate nations and their individuals.

The epic text is overloaded with sociological aspects intrinsic to the culture and faith of the people where the plot takes place, which makes it clear that it is a society, an environment where everything is controlled; Therefore, the interpretation cannot be based on the thinking of another society, especially if it is already very distant in chronological space. Hence, the reader must seek to know, as much as possible, the elements that determined the direction of collective beliefs, because this is another detail in the sociology of these ancient people; there was no concept of individuality, which did not allow them to create Psychology. Therefore, everything described in classical and epic texts from the Ancient Age makes reference to social behaviors and not to individual feelings.

When the poet describes the Garden of Eden, calling it *Paradise*, this is a question of the poet's introspective inferential interpretation, because this is a classification given to something that can be taken as wonderful and not as if it were so and, the its construction was not without the dangers that all nature commonly offers to all mortals.

The biblical text says that God placed there, in the Garden of Eden, a special creature, whom he called *Adan*, which in Hebrew means born of clay. This represents the first man, a word that derives from the Sanskrit *homo*, which means humus, clay, clay. This already characterizes the human being as an indefinite creature, who has not been given the right to even know what he is.

Here is the most surprising question in the book of Genesis: Why did God say, "Let us make man in our image, after our likeness?" and, in the next verse, the poet says: "And God created man in his own image; in the image of God he created him; male and female he created them." And further on it says that God blessed them, and said to them: Be fruitful and multiply,

and fill the earth, and subdue it; and have dominion over the fish of the sea and over the birds of the air, and over every living thing that moves on the earth” (GENESIS, 1, verses 26-28).

And what most attracts attention is that the garden, in fact, an oasis, was created and man was placed there, so that he could take care of it and watch over the creatures that lived there. And, this clarification leads to the understanding that the human being was created in another environment and, at some point, was taken there.

In the first part of the poem, we get the idea that the story deals with a time when the Hebrew nation was polytheistic; considering that the Creator God exhorts others to build the human being together, in his image and likeness and more, it was a strictly patriarchal culture, because it talks about creating *man*. In the second part of the text, the archaic text is reproduced, with the following wording that God created man and woman, male and female, so that they could procreate and be fruitful. And, another thing that causes concern is that, in the same verse (verse 27), it says that he created them *in the image of God*, when the correct wording, if he were referring to God-Creator himself, would be, *he created them in his own image. image...*

This sequence of cuts and textual juxtaposition, conditions, *sui generis*, which induce dubious thoughts and interpretative difficulties, leads to an understanding that the original story is not of Hebrew origin but, possibly, Vedic, transcribed from Sanskrit and inserted in the Old Testament by several poets at different times in the history of the Hebrew nation.

Only in the third part of the text does the poet who continued historical thought portray *Paradise* as the personification of human childhood, with all its glimpses, mishaps, challenges and disappointments that accompany it. The account given of the type of existence experienced by the two characters is characteristic and representative of the human existence that is experienced to this day, without any variations that can be understood, despite the time lapse between the production of the epic and this analysis. The poet leads us to think that his description is about a human phylogenetic aspect, built on existentialist poetry, which makes many readers take this part of the text as a historical report.

It is never less than clear that the Bible is a complex book, precisely because its creation is the product of the collection of several stories that occurred at different times and these were brought together in a single volume, already late and many parts of the original texts, possibly, had already been lost, due to the action and weather caused by not so careful storage and, in the organization, many things were translated, others interpreted and still others filled in according to what the scribe assumed, based on his knowledge or from of your ignorance on the subject. Therefore, the reader, in many cases, does not know whether he is reading a historical story or a poetic story and takes it according to his individual training.

THE GARDEN OF EDEN

The name derives from the Akkadian *edinnu*, which comes from the Sumerian word *edin*, which means *plain* or *steppe* and is closely related to an Aramaic root word meaning *fruitful and well-watered*. Another interpretation associates the name with a Hebrew word for *pleasure*; thus the Douay-Rheims Bible, in Genesis 2:8, has the expression: *And the Lord God had planted a paradise of pleasure, instead of a garden in Eden*. The Hebrew term is translated as *pleasure* in Sarah's secret saying in Genesis 18:12.

Once again, here we have two interpretations being attributed to two clearly distinct objects, but due to the interpretation that was assumed by the medieval translators of the Bible, the impression that was left is that we are dealing with of a single object, a wonderful place and, at the same time, human, all too human, because in its domain there was a tree whose fruit allowed the acquisition of knowledge and discernment between good and evil and, also, there was a tree whose fruit held the power over death and an interesting question may arise as to why they did not immediately decide to eat this fruit. The answer is the most logical one can have: if both inhabitants of the garden were unaware of themselves and their conditions as human beings, how could they have any abstract thought about existence? The characters inserted in the story had just been born; There was no other human they could compare their lives to, much less stories they could hear. What's more, they were born in an extraordinary way; the first, a clay doll, which was given existential life; the other, a product of genetic engineering, produced from DNA. Not satisfied, there was a strange animal in the garden, a snake and, judging that it was the only snake present there, it was very imposing and its presence did not pose any risk to the lives of either of them; which can be deduced that it was a totem animal of worship, a kind of goddess, which already introduces an Egyptian character into the story, since the *snake goddess* was a figure worshiped among them.

Every time the poet refers to the Garden that is present in Eden, he is making an allusion to a geographical space created and organized in such a way that it contrasted with the entire desert region that permeates the arid zone around Judah. It could be a place located to the south, where the rivers that bathed it came from glaciers that were more distant and, the report of its existence can be the description of oral stories transmitted by ancient generations and not a mere imaginative construction of some creative author.

Everything that is said about the garden is a reference to an oasis in the middle of an arid desert region; not a metaphor. Even the tree of the knowledge of good and evil may not be

a simple story but rather a special condition in which the fruit of this species possessed hallucinogenic powers and its ingestion was part of some rite of passage, in which when the child reached certain age, would be submitted as a way of receiving the title of *adult man* . If this can be deduced from the situation, Adan's crime was to consume him without respecting all the tradition that was followed and what would be passed on to the new man as *teachings* had been applied to him as a punishment, a *retribution* for his crime and his access to the garden was strictly prohibited; to him, for having committed a serious crime and to Eva, for having induced him to do so.

The crime of Adan and his companion, we must pay very special attention to this expression, because the semantic meaning of this word, in archaic times and even when the Old Testament was written, was what referred to the wife, in contemporary vocabulary. . So, both were already formally married; Why, how else would a woman have so much persuasive power over a man? Hebrew traditions report that among these people it was customary for the couple to unite and spend a period of six months in union without consummating the marriage through carnal union.

Quite possibly, all the children, as they reached adulthood, left that wonderful and safe garden to seek refuge in other spaces and create their own spaces of living and existence, creating their own family, founding villages, tribes, clans, phratry , and could become cities. The Garden of Eden is a reference in the middle of a point, a place that everyone considered to be blessed by God for its beauty and abundance, given the climatological conditions and abundance of water.

According to the account in Genesis 2:8, Eden was a very vast region, which was possibly formed by extensive plains, with its summit ending with a hill or even a mountain, judging by the formation of fresh waters, which already reveals that it had glaciers at its highest point. To state “And the Lord God planted a garden in Eden, on the east side” (Genesis 2:8) the poet is referring to an extensive region and the legendary garden grew at a branching point of the river that was born on the summits from the mountain of Eden: “And a river came out of Eden to water the garden; and from there it divided and became four arms” (Genesis 2:10).

If the garden was in Eden, how could a river come out to supply this same space? These are two expressions referred to by two poets at different times, because the first author already states that the aforementioned garden is located north of Eden, in a lucid reference that this place (Eden) is a point of geographic determination. Therefore, the expression, Jardim do Eden represents *the force of linguistic expression* , and cannot be interpreted *ipsis litteris* .

HUMAN EXISTENCE IN THE GARDEN OF EDEN

“And the Lord God took the man, and put him in the garden of Eden to work it and keep it” (Genesis 2:15). This passage reveals that Adan, the first man, lived in the southern region of Eden; possibly an arid, desert and also quite inhospitable region, because it is only when he is taken to the garden, which is on the northern slope of Eden, that he encounters previously unknown animal specimens, that is, he had not had contact with any of them. In the same reading we have to say that he already had to work, to till the land in the garden in order to obtain his sustenance and, at the same time, to protect him from other tribes.

Possibly, it took many years for this region, which could well have been difficult to access, to be discovered by the people who lived in the southern part of Eden which, as already discussed, could well be a very high mountain and its discovery represents a condition bold for the time, because the place of geographic origin of man is diametrically opposed to the described geographic location of the garden.

Once installed there, the man took care of creating his laws and imposing his already traditional customs in his native land and a few other things that he may have deemed necessary for the full development of his community. As the people who migrated to the northern region of Eden were people of the desert, it is natural that they took with them the cult of the serpent goddess *Mater* and, therefore, when the poet went to write the stories of the Hebrew people, already under the custom of worshipping the god The sole, male *pater* made a point of punishing those who gave in to the worship of the Goddess, giving her worship, making it very clear that her cults were led by women and this was enough for Adan and his companion to return to the region located to the south, from where the first families had left towards the north. From this analysis, it is clear that Eden represented a geographical landmark, in which on one side there was a land marked by intense abundance, with many minerals, gold, abundant pastures that allowed intensive animal husbandry and the other marked by intense difficulties. of production in every sense.

As it is a region where the existence of a water flow that divides into four branches is described, forming quite large rivers that were responsible for the formation of great civilizations, it is believed that the legendary garden was very extensive in geographic area. ; It is not a forest as contemporary imagination might lead us to understand.

Considering the expression that, after the fall of Adan, two heavily armed angels began to protect the *tree of life*, this expression could be a metaphor for the water sources, since it was from there that the fresh waters that guaranteed all life for the people who lived below and

on the banks of these rivers. It reveals that the control of such sources was already an object of dispute, because their dominance would represent absolute power over a large part of the Eastern world. Analyzing from this perspective, the great interest in protecting the Garden of Eden was to maintain control over that region and the entire area that extended to the banks of the rivers that formed there. Unfortunately, the data that has reached the present day is incipient in interpreting the entire geographic dimension of the region of Eden and the poet took care to create a romantic and, at the same time, tragic situation to explain the supposed origin and supposed fall of the Eden. man, based on a condition of disobedience on the part of his companion and his adherence to the designs of an outsider god. Adan and his wife are not only expelled from the Garden; They are repatriated to the region where they were originally from and where life was very hard, due to the geographical and climatological conditions.

The text of the book of Genesis 1 and 2 undermines the idea that Adan was created in the Garden of Eden itself. On the contrary, his partner was raised there, which leads us to think that she was the daughter of other families who were also taken to that place in order to take care of the place. As the writing of the text is a mixture of many ancient reports, what we have are conditions of interpretation crossed by difficulties in locating elements that contribute to proving the thesis presented. When the elements are taken separately, there is an approach to clarifying the judgments presented; but, when they all come together, forming a chain of thoughts, an incoherence in the distribution of data is perceived in a way that makes it possible to create a linear story.

The so-called Garden of Eden is a reality and cannot be confused with what was called *paradise on Earth*, because it is a natural geographical construction that has been the target of many battles and interests, including the maintenance of a particular culture and customs, which represents a normal attitude among the people and everything that has been reported is incipient to carry out a broader defense about what, in fact, happened there for Adan and his wife to be, literally, expelled. The data analyzed and what remains hidden between the lines was what gave rise to worship of a god who thought he was subjugated and this sparked an astounding fear that the serpent goddess would once again have devout followers.

REFERENCE TO THE GARDEN OF EDEN AS PARADISE: A REPRESENTATIVE METAPHOR OF HUMAN CHILDHOOD

In the passages of the Bible in which reference is made to the Garden of Eden, given its beauty and uniqueness, one can adopt the poetic expression that it was a paradisiacal place, an

epic construction, because there was a contrast with which one could compare, the desert and almost inhospitable areas located south of the Eden region. However, there are some translations of the Bible or some interpretations of authors who are quick to understand metaphors as literal expressions and, when placing them in poetic contexts, there is a distorted understanding of the facts and, when taken by common sense as a common expression, its consecration is achieved and it becomes corroborated as an autonomous truth.

In Genesis 3:23, the passage says that God expelled Adan from the Garden of Eden and not from *paradise*, as it reads *in verbis*: “the Lord God expelled him from the garden of Eden, so that he could cultivate the land from which he had been taken” (Gen. 3:23). This statement only reinforces what has already been discussed in other passages of this text. What is important to discuss from now on is what motivated Catholic priests to interpret this passage as an allusion to paradise and how this was added to common sense in such a way that individuals make use of both expressions as if they were dealing with same thing.

It begins by clarifying that, until the 18th century (of the current era), childhood was not considered a paradise, but rather a hell and, the nomenclature itself, derives from the semantic term *infant, one who does not speak and, so to speak, passage, this expression has nothing to do with the lack of organization of the child's linguistic structure, meaning exactly what it expresses, in which they should remain silent wherever they are. Etymologically, the word childhood originates from the Latin *infantia*, from the verb *fari* = to speak, where *fan* = speaker and *in* constitutes the negation of the verb. Therefore, *infans* refers to the individual who is not yet able to speak. If this were the case, childhood would last until just beyond the age of two and not until the age of twelve, a concept adopted by the Child and Adolescent Statute (Law 8069/90) (BRASIL, 1990).*

See what is described in the gospels, considered apocryphal, about children who were considered to have rebellious behavior: “If a man has a rebellious and stubborn child, who does not obey his father or mother and does not listen when they discipline him, let him Your father and mother hold you at the house gate and call the elders of the city. Parents must say: 'This child is stubborn and rebellious, he does not obey us, he is a gluttonous drunkard'. Then, all the men in the city must stone her to death. In this way, you will remove the devil from your midst and all the children of Israel will hear and be afraid” (MAXIMILIANO, 2008, p. 32).

Jesus of Nazareth was one of the men who dared to say that childhood was a privileged place and that children were pure in their feelings; It is logical that his intention was to cause a scandal in his time, opposing the ideas of the gluttonous priests who dominated the political scene. When he says: “Let the children come to me, do not hinder them; for the Kingdom of

God belongs to those who are like them” (Mark, 10:13-14) such words sounded like poison in the ears of the Jewish leaders.

Even with all the dominance of the Catholic Church and Christianity, childhood was ignored as a paradise until, in 1762, Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) published his *mangum opus, Emile or Education*, in which he conditions the child to a specimen devoid of any evil or devious thoughts, that is, the purest manifestation of human innocence and kindness (sic); consequently, it conditions childhood into a paradise, a place of infinite beauty and peace, completely absent of any type of human conflict; that is, from the height of all its perversity, it dehumanizes them. It is clear that Mr. Jacó read the ancient Chinese sages; however, he ignored the Hebrew folk wisdom that says: “Even a child shows what he is by his actions; her behavior will reveal whether she is pure and righteous” (PROVERBS, 20:11).

It is very obvious that this perverse thought was absorbed by the priests who followed Monsieur Rousseau and, together with institutional Christianity, Pedagogy took care to adopt it, which led to a decline in taste and the concept of the common being, equating childhood with paradise and, to make matters worse, assimilating it to the story of Adam, his ruin and his consequent expulsion from the Garden of Eden. This place described in the Bible, if taken within a precept of semantic expression, cannot be called paradise, using a noun, but rather, it can be given an adjectival phrase, a *paradisiacal place*, once the comparison with the lands inhospitable and desert areas that existed south of Eden. In the same proportionality of expression of thought, childhood is seen as a paradisiacal human existential stage, when compared with adult life and all its vicissitudes, challenges and responsibilities that determine it.

At this point in the argument we reach a determinant of inflection, in which, when you have something to compare with and one of these objects is common and the other singular, the way to determine it is to use an adjective with interpretative power. of sublimation, that is, what would a paradise be, within a semantic concept? It can be attributed a surreal character, not capable of being imagined because its description is poetic and romanticized, obeying the criteria of freedom that the person who describes the scene created by him has.

Some authors even dare to interpret Nietzsche's (1844-1900) *Übermensch* (the beyond man) as being the human representation of the existential infantile stage. This is going far beyond what is reasonable and forcing the German thinker to agree with Rousseau's French trickery about childhood. Poetically, such comparisons can even be admitted; but, within the scope of medical, psychological and pedagogical sciences, all of this is nothing more than

common sense constructions that were absorbed by intellectuals and ended up being taken as unquestionable truths.

This discussion is so complex and has such a sociological character and not medical, pedagogical or psychological, as it is intended to be attributed, in which all these sciences obey the dictates of sociological determinism that childhood becomes a relevant subject from the Second Industrial Revolution (between 1850 and 1870) due to the lack of labor to work in industry. I could no longer admit the staggering mortality rates within one year of life (around 750 for every 1000 live births, without any modesty). From this, a medical discourse began to emerge in which children's lives were valued and a concern with offering care for their survival and, nevertheless, all other categories took a ride, transforming childhood into an immaculate human existential paradise.

At the beginning of the 20th century, Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) caused another scandal in Victorian society by stating that childhood is not a place free from conflicts, that is, it cannot be understood as the paradise described by intellectuals and that, these Special types of conflicts, common to children, are expressed under a bias of desire for possession and fear of losing an object that is considered a sexual representation. For Rousseau's furious widows, the child would be a representation of the asexual doll very common in convenience stores and children's artifacts.

In the same way that Rousseau distorted childhood, making it a place without any kind of conflict, so contemporary priests and supposed intellectuals did with the Garden of Eden, depriving it of biological and agronomic needs, making it a surreal and their inhabitants into strange, non-human herbivorous creatures. There is a total distortion of the existential process of life on Earth, which can only exist in the thoughts of a lunatic, and it is from this rhetorical sleight of hand that the metaphor of paradise was created to refer to the historical garden mentioned in Bible and then associate the human existence of two individuals immersed in it with the human developmental stage of childhood, linking the issue of biological knowledge, a phylogenetic condition inherent to the species, to the human being's passage to adulthood as a [*forced and brutal*] unraveling of which He feels homesick for his entire life, understanding the term "saudade" under the condition of expectation that one day he will be able to return to it. It all comes down to metaphors created with the aim of manipulating public opinion in favor of some ideological power project. It was very easy to associate the two metaphors, because in the same way that adults live immersed and consumed by the latent desire to return to their childhood; Thus, Adan also lived his days in the latent expectation of returning to the Garden of Eden. Both were expelled from their romantic homes without any plausible explanation;

They are sentenced to endless torture and, in the end, the only thing clear in their lives is that things *have been like that* since the beginning.

CONCLUSION

The Garden of Eden, an element expressed and reported in the book of Genesis, can very well be interpreted as an allegory given the poetic condition to which it was subjected over the centuries and the romanticization to which it was subjected, especially to characterize the misfortune of Adan and his companion, Eva. It turns out that, given the analytical aspects and the description of its geographical location and the climatological phenomena, it is believed that it was real, representing a vast region located on the side of a mountain, watered by springs that came from from above and which, on the slope described, unfolded into bodies of water, forming historic rivers, on the banks of which very powerful nations rose.

All the study carried out so far has allowed us to reach the conclusion that, given the beauty performances and special conditions of geographical existence, the place could be categorized as *paradisiacal*, never as a paradise, simply because it was not one. Everything that was built on statements about his miraculous condition was a creation of common sense, hasty interpretations that had no connection with the texts that describe him.

In the interpretations that followed, in which the condition of stating that the Garden of Eden is a paradise is used, it is a confusion in which an attempt is made to directly link the history of two individuals to it, without making the appropriate temporal and existential cut. . It was assumed, based on the understanding that childhood is a wonderful and conflict-free place, that it is also a *paradise* and, everything became capable of being correlated, in which, in the same way that normal humans are expelled from this paradise by *Physis* , God expelled Adan and Eve from what was supposed to be treated as such.

To elaborate the linguistic determination, they first took care to transform the two historical characters into idiots and, to relate them to childhood, they dehumanized the children, depriving them of any and all types of feelings that could provoke and/or awaken conflicts. Having achieved this wonderful feat, the next step was to treat childhood as a paradise and spread the idea of the absolute purity of children, based on the understanding of the words of Jesus of Nazareth about them, which were corroborated by Rousseau, in his *magnum opus* , in 1762 and which became a blessing when the professional market needed labor for work in industry.

What we have here is a distorted idea about something that we had no knowledge of, because since the Greeks, no people have been interested in childhood, so much so that in Greece and even in Sparta, children were in the care of their mothers until they were seven years old. deity. This is just one more reason to be considered a paradisiacal moment in the human lives of these individuals, compared to what awaited them next.

The expression *paradise* is not expressed in the biblical texts of the *Old Testament*, being nothing more than a metaphor created by the priest poets of the Middle Ages and which found support in the social, psychological, pedagogical and theological sciences to raise the idea *ad infinitum* in common sense, without any of them worrying about deepening their understanding of the topic.

Even the expression *garden*, used to refer to the region of Eden where beauty and wild natural wealth abounded, is a metaphorical condition, because it is not a forest but rather a very long area. Poetic linguistic constructions were being created by creative individuals and it could even be Adam and his wife himself who reported the wonders of such a space, since they were there as guests and could testify to its grandeur and exuberance and that, when compared with the region where they lived, this comparison allowed us to conclude that this idyllic place was *a true paradise*.

The authors, in order to correlate the Garden of Eden with human childhood, creating the intellectual link that both things are a paradise, express that the spirit of God took long walks at dusk with man through paradise. This behavior is a human phylogenetic condition, in which parents tend to walk with their children in the afternoon, indulging in a type of happiness that is very rare and special for the species and that leaves a deep longing for parents when their children are no longer interested. In such type of behavior, being portrayed with a deep sense of nostalgia.

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